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Comparative Analysis of Heterogeneous Bio-Catalysts for the Production of Bio-Diesel from Pork Lard

**Madu Paul Chukwunonso^a, Edwin Nwabuo Ikezue,
Joseph Okechukwu Ezeugo, Ibiam Prince Amauche^b**

Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Uli, Anambere State, Nigeria

^{a,b}E-mail address: madupaulc@yahoo.com , ibiamprince72@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Large scale biodiesel production was produced through Trans esterification of oil from pork lard with methanol and calcium oxide (CaO) obtained from biological sources as catalysts using batch mode. The physicochemical properties of CaO catalysts obtained from chicken eggshells and pawpaw leaves were characterized and effects of key parameters like reaction temperature, reaction time, catalyst concentration and methanol/oil molar ratio were determined using batch mode. These researches has experimentally develop a new method for lard by using suitable conditions of production with solvent blending. A polynomial equation was obtained for lard biodiesel yields as a function of synthesis parameters. The validity of the predictive model was confirmed by validation experiments. The suitable combination for high quality biodiesel production from lard was less than 2.0 wt. % catalyst with 10:1 methanol/lard molar ratio and 65.0 wt. % solvent additive. The significant point of this method was to use high solvent blending ratios for lard synthesis to overcome poor solubility problems between highly concentrated free fatty acid pork lard and catalyst. Using this method, gave high yields of biodiesel in short reaction time. The evaluation of the synthesis was made using gas chromatography. The final products fulfilled all the requirements of ASTM D6751-09 and EN 142:4 standards. Overall, this process can be useful for larger scale industrial process with low energy consumption.

Keywords: Comparative Analysis, Heterogeneous, Bio-Catalysts, Production Bio-Diesel, Pork Lard

1. INTRODUCTION

Alternative fuels must be environmentally acceptable and economically competitive. Research on biodiesel (BD) derived from vegetable oils and animal fat is being conducted to alternate this kind of fuels with petroleum-based diesel fuel. The waste frying oils are known to be scarce but waste animal fats are more abundant and inexpensive. Animal fat BD has higher cetane number, and it more prone to oxidation than diesel fuel. BD from animal fat contains no aromatic moieties and almost no Sulphur [1, 2].

It contains a high oxygen concentration by weight, is biodegradable, and has high lubricant ability. But the use of animal fat BD fuels has not been developed in depth. Several research studies have been carried out on the BD production from pork lard. Temperature and catalyst amount are the most important parameters determining the BD quality. Immobilized lipase catalyzed BD production from lard gives a BD yield of 87.4 wt. % with 8 wt. % solvent (n-hexane) blending. Also, BD production yields from animal fat varied from 81.7-88.0 wt. % without solvent blending. BD production from chicken and mutton fats using an acid catalyst resulted in higher yield in comparison to base catalysis. As long-time reaction requires high energy consumption, the final product price always increase 4.

Many studies report statistical analysis to optimize the parameters influencing the synthesis process in various vegetable oils. But only a few studies to optimize lard synthesis process have been carried out. Found a regression equation describing the relation between the fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) concentration of BD and the operational variables (catalyst concentration and agitation speed). They reported that for lard synthesis, the most important variable is the catalyst concentration [3] compared two types of catalyst, methanol/oil molar ratio, and reaction time effects to lard methyl ester extraction and reported that the under optimal conditions, BD yield reached to 97.2 wt. % with methanol/oil molar ratio of 5.12 and reaction time of 20h. "Bio" indicates a source of energy that is biological and renewable; "diesel" means it can be used only in diesel engines [4]. Biodiesel can be used directly in a diesel engine in its neat pure form called B100 (100% biodiesel) or in a blend with different proportions of conventional diesel fuels. Common blends include B20 (20% biodiesel and 80% conventional diesel), which are much closer to diesel fuel properties than B100 and B5 (5% biodiesel and 95% conventional diesel). Biodiesel may become a gel in cold weather since its cloud point is generally higher than conventional diesels. Addition of cold flow additives can prevent it from gelling at a low temperature.

Biodiesel solvent can cause degradation of rubbers and elastomers. Using low-percentage biodiesel blends can mitigate the degradation, but the compromise will somewhat lessen the positive environmental benefits. Biodiesel emissions contain more smog-forming nitrous oxide (NO_x) than conventional diesels, which may delay the injection timing of engines. Increase in demand for energy, instability of the prices of fossil fuels in international market, depletion of the sources resulting from their non-renewable nature, political tensions associated with fossil fuels, more consciousness about the environment and more have led to search for an alternative fuel which can supplement or replace fossil fuels.

Biodiesel is a renewable fuel mainly produced by Tran's esterification of oils and fats that can be used as a transportation fuel, solvent and for energy generation with the potential to reduce the emissions of CO₂, SO₂, CO and hydrocarbons, compared to fossil fuels [5].

Biodiesel is considered as one of the most alternative fuel for diesel engines and it is nontoxic, renewable and biodegradable.

Besides, biodiesel present many advantages such as a high cetane number, high flash point, lubricity properties, biodegradability and environmentally friendliness [6]. Biodiesel is a renewable fuel of key importance to meet environmental and economic sustainability. Biodiesel, a form of bioenergy is produced by trans esterification which is a chemical process that involves reversible reaction between the triglyceride in vegetable oils or animal fats with short chain alcohol such as methanol or ethanol on an alkaline, acid or enzyme catalyst to yield a mixture with at least 96wt% of fatty acid methyl ester or fatty acid ethyl ester (FAME or FAEE) and glycerol [7]. The Trans esterification process has some difficulties due to the presence of free fatty acids (FFA) and water content.

Thus, requires high quality raw materials to avoid side reactions and saponification. To overcome the cost of production, concerted efforts are made to use readily available and low-cost raw materials for its production. For instance, animal fats are now preferred feedstocks for biodiesel production. In addition, animal shell and plant seeds (rich in CaCO_3) are the raw materials processed as CaO catalyst. By so doing, the environmental pollution problems arising from the wrong disposal of the large volume of animal shells, plant seeds and animal fat are minimized [8]. CaO has been widely reported as a suitable heterogeneous form of catalyst due to its high reusability, high selectivity and high biodiesel yield [9], and this CaO heterogeneous catalyst used in biodiesel production involves the processing of animal shells and plant seed skin and leaves wastes that are rich in CaCO_3 . These waste materials include egg shells, periwinkle shells, fish bones, pawpaw seed, pawpaw skin, pawpaw leaves etc. In addition, the use of CaO catalyst from wastes promotes stable and highly efficient catalytic performance, produces low freezing point biodiesel, and enhances high surface area and uniform porosity of the catalysts as well as excellent water and acid resistance ability [10]. A high percentage of the current investigations in the domain of biodiesel production is oriented toward the design of suitable solid catalysts, either with acid or alkaline properties. Each has various advantages and disadvantages. So, it will be correct to choose according to raw materials and working conditions. These are basically divided into two classes as homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts. The conventional catalysts are alkali metal hydroxides and alkoxides namely homogeneous strong bases and homogeneous acids such as H_2SO_4 .

Alkali-catalyzed Tran's esterification is much faster than acid-catalyzed. Homogeneous base catalysts generally cause corrosion in the equipment and also lead to the formation of undesired by-products that requires separation steps. This extra separation step increases the cost. Homogeneous acid catalysts are difficult to recycle and operate at high temperatures. They also cause corrosion and serious environmental problems. In this study, efforts have been taken to review the studies that are about the biodiesel production from animal fat using CaO, a bio-catalyst. As energy demands increase and fossil fuels are limited, research is directed towards alternative renewable fuels. Biomass has been found to produce low-molecular weight organic liquids, which can be used or proposed for vehicles. A potential diesel oil substitute is biodiesel, consisting of methyl esters of fatty acids produced by the two-step methods; hydrolysis reaction of triglycerides of vegetable oils or animal fat and then esterification reaction with methanol with the help of a catalyst [11].

Due to the great molecular similarities of biodiesel to paraffinic diesel fuel compounds, this alternative fuel has a chance of fulfilling the demands that diesel engine makes of its fuel. Essentially, no engine modifications are required to substitute biodiesel for diesel fuel that can maintain the engine performance. In addition, biodiesel is better than diesel fuel in terms of sulphur content, flash point, aromatic content and biodegradability.

The growing demand for renewable energy sources has intensified interest in biodiesel production as a sustainable alternative to fossil fuels. Among various feedstocks, pork lard, a by-product of the meat industry, presents an opportunity for biodiesel production [12]. However, traditional methods of biodiesel synthesis often face challenges related to efficiency, cost and environmental impact.

Heterogeneous bio catalysts have emerged as a promising solution to enhance the Trans esterification process, offering advantages such as easier separation and reuse compared to homogeneous catalysts. Despite these potential benefits, there is limited comparative analysis of different heterogeneous bio catalysts specifically for biodiesel production from pork lard.

By systemically analyzing various heterogeneous bio catalysts and their performance in biodiesel production from pork lard, this research seeks to identify the most effective and sustainable options for industrial applications [13]. The findings will contribute to the advancement of biodiesel technologies and promote the utilization of waste fats thereby supporting the transition to renewable energy sources.

2. EXPERIMENTAL (MATERIALS AND METHODS)

2. 1. Extraction and Pretreatment of Waste Animal Fats into Oil

As earlier discussed in chapter two of this literature, fats from pork lard were found in the form of fat-protein matrix at adipose tissue. Waste fat from animal carcasses is removed and then made into an oil using a rendering process. Rendering consists of grinding the animal by-products to a fine consistency and cooking them until the liquid fat separates and pathogens are destroyed.

The experiment was conducted in the laboratory scale setup which consisted of a 2000 ml flask and the reaction mixture agitated by a magnetic stirrer at 600 rpm. A sample of 300 ml of lard was placed in a flat bottom flask. The lard was heated to 55-60 °C. In another beaker, methanol (considering a methanol/lard molar ratio of 6:1, 10:1 and 14:1) was mixed with 0.48-3.05 wt. % catalysts. This mixture was then added to the melted lard and stirred rigorously for 120 mins.

The mixture was then transferred to a separate funnel and glycerol was allowed to separate. After draining off the glycerol, BD was washed to remove excess of methanol. Finally, the lard was distilled to remove the residual water and solvent. **Note:** Fats whose FFA% exceeds more than 5%, must undergo necessary pretreatment before being carried out to trans esterification reaction. Pork lard fat having FFA% of more than 5% contains unhydrolyzed triglycerides so therefore, the FFA are esterified in order to form monoglycerides, which can be transesterified for biodiesel production. Commonly used acid catalyst, sulfuric acid was used for reducing the FFA% below 0.5-1%, before been transesterified with any other catalysts [14].

2. 2. Materials, Reagents and Equipment's

Some of the materials and reagents used include waste animal fat from pork lard (herein after referred to as "lard"), chicken eggshells, pawpaw leaves, methanol (99.5 wt.%), CaO catalyst from eggshell and pawpaw leaves, 650 ml Na₂CO₃, 20 ml H₂SO₄, 100 ml Na₂SO₄. Some of the equipment used in this research work include Gas Chromatography Mass Spectroscopy (Agilent Technologies 7890 A, GC System/5975C VL MSD, USA, for the identification and determination of percentage composition n of fatty acids in the animal fat), Atomic Absorption

Spectroscopy (Analyst 200 Perkin Elmer precisely, USA, for the identification and quantification of the heavy metals (potential emissions) from biodiesel) and also for the identification and quantification of the metals present in the prepared pawpaw leaves, XRF spectroscopy (Thermo Scientific ARL OP-TIM'X 166, to determine the elemental compositions of the catalysts), XRD spectroscopy (bruker D5005, to determine the crystalline nature of the catalyst) and Scanning Electronic Microscope (ME 600T polarizing optical microscope, to examine the size or morphology of the catalysts), reflux condenser (used to cool the vapours that heated fluids emit and change their physical state back to liquid by means of a straight, spiraled or coiled circulation cooling method and to prevent material loss from vaporization).

2. 3. Catalyst Preparation Using Waste Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves

The raw chicken eggshells obtained from Federal Polytechnic Nekede Cafeteria were carefully washed in pure water for obtaining a better material for the catalyst preparation free of contaminants and then dried in an oven for 45 minutes at 110 °C to remove water present.

The dried eggshells were then crushed in a mechanical grinder to fine particulate size then sieved on an automated sieve to obtain < 75 µm particle sizes. The dried sample which has been subjected to size reduction is done in order to improve the surface area which is a major factor that affects the speed of the reaction [15]. The fine powdered was then dried in the oven for 30 minutes at 110 °C to remove any other moisture content present.

Calcination of the fine powdered was carried out in a Muffle furnace (Carbolite HTF 1700) at 850 °C for 3 hours and at this temperature, chicken eggshell CaO catalyst was obtained. The chicken eggshells CaO catalyst obtained was then stored in an air tight container to prevent the CaO catalyst from poison by reacting with air in the environment. For quality calcinations, sample should be uniform [16]. Fig. 1, illustrated the preparation process of waste-eggshell derived catalyst.

Figure 1. Preparation of CaO catalyst derived from eggshell waste.

For CaO obtained from *Carica papaya*, a sample of the *Carica papaya* leaves was collected from mile two lane, federal polytechnic nekede, owerri and was identified at Department of food science and technology, federal polytechnic nekede, Owerri, imo state.

The samples of the green leaves of papaya were sorted, washed and shade-dried for three (3) days and was subsequently ground to powder using household blender.

Figure 2. Flow chart showing the processing of pawpaw leaves.

Five hundred gram (500 g) of each of the blended leaves of papaya was macerated in 1.5 litres of methanol for 48 hours, the solution was filtered with Whatman no.-4 filter paper, then centrifuged and decanted to remove the remaining particles. The extract was dried and crushed further to smaller sizes to reduce the particle size which increases the rate of reaction, then calcined in a muffle furnace at 550 °C to obtain calcium.

The proximate composition of the extract made from carica papaya leaves was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) and the moisture, crude protein, crude fat, total ash, crude fibre and carbohydrate content were determined using the methods described by AOAC analysis. Calcium, Copper, Iron, Zinc, Magnesium, Potassium, Phosphorus, Chromium and Manganese content of the leaf extract were also determined using the AAS. The study shows the presence of the following minerals- phosphorus (26.153 mg / 100g), iron (326.121 mg / 100g), potassium (2107.800 mg/ 100g), calcium (3809.329 mg / 100g) and chromium (7.448 mg / 100g) [17]. The calcium hydroxide concentrate obtained from the pawpaw leaves were reacted with sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃) to produce calcium carbonate and sodium hydroxide.

The calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) was thermally decomposed at 800 °C to produce calcium oxide (CaO), liberating carbon dioxide.

The physiochemical characteristics of the CaO catalyst derived from chicken eggshells and pawpaw leaves were carried out through SEM and XRF analysis.

Figure 3. Processing of the pawpaw leaves to CaO catalyst.

2. 4. Experimental Setups

Figures 4 and 5 show a schematic diagram and photographs of the experimental setup designed for the alkali-trans esterification study. The setup was designed to facilitate three consecutive steps of operation: preheating methanol, trans esterification reaction, and product separation.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the alkali-catalyzed trans esterification experimental setup.

Reactors connected with condensers

Water bath for preheating methanol

Separating funnels

Figure 5. Photographs of the alkali-catalyzed trans esterification experimental setup.

Design Expert software (version 11.1.0.1) was used in this study to design the experiment and to optimize the reacting conditions. The experimental design employed in this work was a central composite design (CCD), a two-level-four-factor including 30 experiments. Methanol/oil molar ratio, A, Catalyst concentration, B, reaction temperature, C and reaction time, D were selected as independent factors for the optimization study. The response chosen was the methyl ester yields obtained from trans esterification of animal fat. As usual, the experiments were performed in random order to avoid systematic error [18]. The regression analysis was performed to estimate the response function as a second order polynomial as shown in equation 3.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{ii} X_i^2 + \sum_{i=1, i < j}^{k-1} \sum_{j=2}^k \beta_{ij} X_i X_j \quad (3)$$

where: Y is the predicted response and β_i , β_{ii} , and β_{ij} are coefficients estimated from regression.

They represent the linear, quadratic and interactions of the independent variables on the response. Selection of levels for each factor was based on the experiments performed to study the effects of process variables on the application of heterogeneous catalysts for trans esterification reaction of animal fat.

The apparatus used for the trans esterification reaction includes:

- (1) One 125 mL glass reactor;
- (2) One reflux condenser, which was connected with the reactor in order to prevent material loss from vaporization;
- (3) One Thermo Scientific Super-Nuova multi-position stirring hot plate to control the reaction temperature and agitation speed;
- (4) One magnetic stirrer to supply a desired mixing intensity; and
- (5) One thermometer to measure the reaction temperature.

2. 5. Experimental Procedure and Conditions

The trans esterification reaction took place in a 125 mL glass reactor. Prior to the reaction, 50 mL of oil extracted from animal fat was added into the reactor, which was placed on a stirring hot plate. The reaction temperature and agitation speed of the stir were adjusted by the stirring hot plate to meet the desired experimental conditions. At the same time, a known amount of CaO derived from chicken eggshell (catalyst) was mixed with a pre-measured amount of methanol. The mixture of catalyst and methanol was then heated to the reaction temperature in a water bath. The trans esterification reaction took place by introducing the mixture of catalyst and methanol to the oil extracted from animal fat in the reactor [19].

The reaction temperature and agitation speed were controlled for a particular period of time until the reaction reached its equilibrium. The final reaction mixture was transferred to a separating funnel and kept undisturbed for 12 hours to separate the glycerol phase and crude biodiesel phase.

The separated glycerol phase in the bottom layer was disposed from the funnel, and a 10 ml crude biodiesel in the top layer was collected and gently washed with 10 ml of deionized water three times to remove the unreacted catalyst, methanol residual, glycerol and trace of soaps. The washed biodiesel was then dried over sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) and injected into a

gas chromatograph with a mass spectrometry detector (GC/MS) for analysis of methyl ester concentration. The experiment was repeated using CaO derived from pawpaw leaves. Figure 6 illustrates the trans esterification experimental procedure in steps. All the experiments were conducted in the fume hood for safety purposes [20]. Experimental conditions for the alkali-catalyzed trans esterification are listed in Table. 1 and the comparison of produced biodiesel from animal fat using CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves in Table. 2.

Figure 6. Experimental procedure for the alkali-catalyzed trans esterification

2. 6. Catalyst Characterization

2. 6. 1. pH Measurement and Colour of Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves Catalysts

The pH of the powdered eggshell was examined before and after calcination to test the alkalinity of the catalyst. As previously mentioned, the higher the alkalinity of the catalyst, the better the yield in trans esterification reaction. The pH values of the eggshell with and without keratin layer did not show any significant differences [21]. Thus, it is not necessary to remove the keratin layer during the preparation of catalyst and this is shown in Table 3. Also, the pH of the pawpaw leaves was examined before and after maceration in methanol and reacting with Na_2CO_3 to test the alkalinity of the catalyst. As previously mentioned, the higher the alkalinity of the catalyst, the better the yield in trans esterification reaction. °

The pH values of the pawpaw leaves after grinding and maceration with methanol and reacting with Na_2CO_3 showed an increase in the alkalinity of the pH value which confirms a better yield in trans esterification as shown in Table 4 and pawpaw leaves produced CaO after thermal decomposition of CaCO_3 at various temperature conditions as shown in Table 5.

2. 6. 2. XRD Analysis of CaO from Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves

Upon calcination process, characterization of catalyst is very important. Eggshells consist of CaCO_3 as a major component and after calcination, this material is converted to CaO. For characterization of the catalyst, XRD analysis is employed. Fig. 7 and 8 shows XRD patterns of catalysts obtained from calcination of chicken eggshell and maceration and thermal treatment of pawpaw leaves at different temperatures respectively. CaCO_3 is major component up to 800 °C in chicken eggshell as shown in Fig 1. Some CaO peaks come up at 700 °C but good conversion is shown beyond 800 °C. As shown in Fig. 7, Calcination step resulted in a change in the XRD pattern for different temperatures, because CO_2 moved away from the starting material due to thermal treatment [22].

The diffraction patterns of the samples heated above 800 °C were related to CaO, while samples heated at temperatures below 800 °C, were related to CaCO₃. The aim of calcination process is conversion of CaCO₃ to CaO so calcination temperature should be above 800 °C. The calcined eggshell between 200 - 1000 °C were tested and gave the CaO catalyst for trans esterification of animal fat to produce biodiesel. According to these results, the catalyst which was calcined above 800 °C was the most active catalyst [23]. The conversion efficiency was obtained to be 97-99% with this catalyst. Besides, as the temperature decreases the yield of trans esterification reaction decreases. Below 600 °C calcination temperature, the yield was obtained as 30%. As shown in Fig. 8, the XRD pattern for pawpaw leaves at above 500 °C shows the diffraction patterns of the samples at the peak were related to CaO, confirming a high percentage of Calcium primarily from grinded pawpaw leaves, macerated with methanol and reacted with Na₂CO₃ to obtain CaCO₃ that was thermally decomposed to CaO giving off CO₂.

2. 6. 3. SEM Analysis of the Catalyst

The morphology of the eggshell waste and thermally treated pawpaw leaves derived catalyst is investigated by SEM. in Fig 9 and Fig 10 respectively which shows the morphological analysis of eggshell and pawpaw leaves at different magnifications. The SEM images show that the prepared catalysts are porous like structure [24]. It reveals the presence of mineral aggregates with macro pores in both catalysts and they can easily bind or mix with methanol and oil. According to the SEM images, the calcined eggshell waste and thermally treated pawpaw leaves typically comprises irregular shape of particles. In other words, there were various sizes and shapes of particles. According to Fig 9 and Fig 10 for eggshell waste and pawpaw leaves respectively, large agglomerates and clusters were formed due to the impact of high temperature and the amount of heat transferred to the sample which caused coalescence between sample particles due to cohesion and adhesion phenomena; consequently, decreased particle size [25]. The smaller size of the grains and aggregates could provide higher specific surface areas, resulting in better catalytic activity.

2. 6. 4. XRF Spectrometry Analysis of the Catalyst

The results of XRF analysis of the two catalysts used during the trans esterification processes are as shown in Table 6. High percentage of CaO was observed in the two samples. The calcination of chicken eggshells powder at 850 °C for 3 hours greatly enhanced the conversion of CaCO₃ (main component of the shell) to CaO. Also, the CaO obtained by reacting the calcium obtained from pawpaw leaves with sodium carbonate produced calcium carbonate liberating sodium [26]. The calcium carbonate was thermally decomposed at 800 °C for 2 hours to produce calcium oxide liberating carbon dioxide which enhanced the conversion of CaCO₃ to CaO. Moreover, the minute quantities of all other compounds (including 5.613% of MgO and 13.742% SiO₂ in chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves respectively) showed that these unwanted compounds could not pose any significant hindrance against the catalytic performance of the two forms of CaO. The chemical compositions of the catalysts are shown in Table 6. The result of the trans esterification process, as shown in Table 7, revealed a similar trend when CaO catalyst obtained from chicken eggshells and CaO obtained from pawpaw leaves were used separately. The yield of biodiesel was slightly higher when using CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell. The slight difference could be attributed to the percentage level of CaO in the two forms of catalysts, as revealed by the XRF analysis (Table 8). An indication that the

production process of CaO from pawpaw leaves requires minor modification for the enhancement of the functionalization of the CaO obtained.

Table 8 shows the material balance for the production of 1 kg of biodiesel using chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and pawpaw leaves CaO catalyst. The result revealed that the production of 1 kg biodiesel (using same quantity of CaO catalyst) would require lesser quantity of both the methanol and animal fat oil in the case of using chicken eggshell CaO catalyst. This is due to the slight difference observed in the percentage of CaO in the two forms of catalyst used.

2. 7. Fatty Acid Composition of Animal Fat Using GCMS

Analysis of the fatty acid composition of animal fat was carried out using GCMS. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 10 and Figure 8. The physico-chemical properties, fatty acid composition and thermal properties of cattle subcutaneous, tallow and intestinal fats were determined. Subcutaneous fat differed from the other fat types with respect to its lower melting point (29.0 °C), higher saponification (211.4 mg KOH/g) and iodine (50.55) values. The cattle fat types contained linoleic acid (18:2), oleic acid (18:1), palmitic acid (16:0), linolenic acid (18:3) and stearic acid (18:0) as the major components of fatty acid composition (36.351%, 31.677%, 13.081%, 7.264% and 5.819%) respectively as shown in Table 8. A differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study revealed that two characteristic peaks were detected in both crystallization and melting curves [27].

2. 8. Identification and Quantification of Heavy Metals in the Biodiesel Using AAS

Potential emissions from both the biodiesel samples were identified and quantified using AAS (Analyst 200 Perkin Elmer precisely, USA). The data obtained were needed in the assessment of the impact of the potential emissions from the biodiesel. Biodiesel samples were first digested (using a solution containing HCl and HNO₃) and then aspirated into the nebulizer compact of AAS where the sample mixed with air and acetone to form a mixture. Flame burned and atomized the sample to the excited state [28]. At excited state, absorption occurred and monochromator selected the wavelength in agreement with the atoms as shown in Table 11.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment in chapter two (2) are as shown in the tables and figures in this chapter.

Table 1. Experiment Conditions for the Alkali-Catalyzed Trans esterification Reaction.

Experimental Parameter	Condition
Methanol to Oil (molar ratio)	9:1
CaO concentration (wt. %)	0.2, 0.6, 1.0
Temperature (°C)	25, 35, 50, 65
Agitation speed (rpm)	200

Table 2. Shows the different reacting conditions with respect to methanol to oil ratio, catalyst concentration, temperature and agitation speed.

Catalyst Type	Conversion Efficiency	Reaction Time	Reusability	Cost - Effectiveness
Lipases	High (70 – 95%)	Moderate (1 – 5 h)	High (up to 5cycles)	Moderate to high
Sulfonic acid resins	Moderate (60 – 80%)	Low (12 – 24 h)	Moderate (3 – 4 cycles)	Moderate
Calcium oxide	Moderate to high (60 – 90%)	Short (1 – 3 h)	Low (1 – 2 cycles)	Low

Table 3. Comparison of Produced Biodiesel from Animal Fat Using CaO Catalyst from Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves.

Properties	Observed Values of Biodiesel produced using CaO from chicken eggshell	Observed Values of Biodiesel produced using CaO from pawpaw leaves	Standard Values of Biodiesel (as per ASTM D6751)
Density (Kg/m ³)	865	870	860 – 900
Kinematic viscosity (mm ² /s) at 40 °C	5.8	6.0	1.9 – 6.0
Specific Gravity	0.87	0.88	0.86 – 0.9
Flash point (°C)	152°C	155°C	100 – 170 °C
Fire point (°C)	162 °C	165 °C	160 – 170 °C
Calorific value (kj/kg)	36970	37272	36000 – 40000
Cetane Number	49	51	47
Higher Heating Value (HHV)	Appro. 37 – 40 MJ/kg	Appro. 37 – 40 MJ/kg	38 MJ/kg
Oxidation Stability (hours)	High up to 6 – 8 hrs	High but may vary (5 – 7 hrs)	High up to 5 – 8 hrs

Table 4. pH measurement of the prepared eggshell catalyst before and after calcination.

Calcination	Material	pH
Before calcination	Eggshell with keratin layer	9.45
	Eggshell without keratin layer	9.61
After calcination	Eggshell with keratin layer	11.93
	Eggshell without keratin layer	11.86

From Table 4, it is shown that before calcination, the pH of the eggshell with and without keratin layer was slightly alkaline, but the calcination process increased the alkalinity of the eggshell and is in conformity with the theory that the higher the alkalinity of the catalyst, the better the yield in trans esterification reaction [29].

Table 5. Eggshell powder after calcination at various conditions.

Calcination temp (°C)	Calcination time (hrs)	Colour
700	2	Black mixed with grey
750	2	Black with little grey
800	2	White with grey
900	1	White with little grey
900	2	White

From Table 5, the eggshell powder colour at different temperatures shows the presence of CaO catalyst. At 900 °C, the colour of the eggshell powder is white which confirms the presence of CaO catalyst. This is also shown in the XRD pattern of chicken eggshell as in Fig. 1.

CaCO₃ is major component up to 800 °C in chicken eggshell as shown in Fig 7. Some CaO peaks come up at 700 °C but good conversion is shown beyond 800 °C. As shown in Fig. 1, Calcination step resulted in a change in the XRD pattern for different temperatures, because CO₂ moved away from the starting material due to thermal treatment [30]. The diffraction patterns of the samples heated above 800 °C were related to CaO, while samples heated at temperatures below 800 °C, were related to CaCO₃.

The pH values of the pawpaw leaves after grinding and maceration with methanol showed an increase in the alkalinity from a pH of 7.05 to a pH of 10.50 which confirms a better yield in trans esterification.

Figure 7. XRD patterns of chicken eggshell and the materials obtained by calcining the chicken eggshell in the range of 200 – 1000 °C.

Table 6. pH measurement of the pawpaw leaves before and after maceration.

	Material	pH
After grinding	Pawpaw leaves sorted, washed, shade dried and grind to power.	7.05
After maceration with methanol	Grinded pawpaw leaves macerated with methanol and filtered with whatman no. - 4 filter paper and reacting with Na ₂ CO ₃	10.50

Table 7. Pawpaw Leaves Produced CaO After Thermal Decomposition of CaCO₃ at Various Temperature Conditions.

Thermal decomposition temp (°C)	Thermal decomposition time (hrs)	Colour
450	2	Green mixed with grey
500	2	Green with little grey
550	1	White with little grey

From Table 7, the pawpaw leaves colour at different temperatures after thermal decomposition shows the presence of CaO catalyst. At 550 °C, the colour of the eggshell powder is white with little grey which confirms the presence of CaO catalyst. This is also shown in the XRD pattern of pawpaw leaves as in Fig. 2.

Figure 8. XRD patterns of grinded pawpaw leaves macerated with methanol and thermally treated.

Figure 8. XRD patterns of grinded pawpaw leaves macerated with methanol and thermally treated. As shown in Fig. 2, the XRD pattern for pawpaw leaves at above 500 °C

shows the diffraction patterns of the samples at the peak were related to CaO, confirming a high percentage of Calcium primarily from grinded pawpaw leaves, macerated with methanol and reacted with Na₂CO₃ to obtain CaCO₃ that was thermally decomposed to CaO giving off CO₂ [31].

Table 8. Chemical Composition of The Catalyst (wt %) using XRF spectrometry analysis.

Compound	Mole% composition of compound from chicken eggshells	Mole% composition of compound from pawpaw leaves
CaO	90.761	51.882
SiO ₂	0.052	13.742
V ₂ O ₅	0.003	0.000
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.002	0.016
MnO	0.039	0.343
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.111	0.400
Co ₃ O ₄	0.014	0.011
NiO	0.031	0.010
CuO	0.052	0.300
Nb ₂ O ₃	0.050	0.005
MoO ₃	0.000	0.005
WO ₃	0.015	0.004
P ₂ O ₅	0.000	0.614
SO ₃	0.000	2.964
MgO	5.613	7.831
K ₂ O	0.136	13.361
BaO	0.000	0.140
Al ₂ O ₃	2.033	4.984
Ta ₂ O ₅	0.009	0.000
TiO ₂	0.000	0.130
ZnO	0.016	0.100
Ag ₂ O	0.000	0.008
Cl	0.697	3.141
ZrO ₂	0.084	0.007
SnO ₂	0.282	0.000

The results of XRF analysis of the two catalysts used during the trans esterification processes are as shown in Table 8. High percentage of CaO was observed in the two samples.

The calcination of chicken eggshells powder at 850 °C for 3 hours greatly enhanced the conversion of CaCO₃ (main component of the shell) to CaO. Also, the CaO obtained by reacting the calcium hydroxide obtained from pawpaw leaves with sodium carbonate produced calcium carbonate that was decomposed to produce calcium oxide liberating carbon dioxide [32].

The calcium carbonate was thermally decomposed at 800 °C for 2 hours to produce calcium oxide liberating carbon dioxide which enhanced the conversion of CaCO₃ to CaO. Moreover, the minute quantities of all other compounds (including 5.613% of MgO and 13.746% SiO₂ in chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves respectively) showed that these unwanted compounds could not pose any significant hindrance against the catalytic performance of the two forms of CaO. The chemical compositions of the catalysts are shown in Table 7.

Table 9. Material Balance on 1 Kg of Biodiesel Produced Using the Two Different Catalysts and wash water.

Feeds	Quantity of CaO eggshell (kg)	Quantity of CaO pawpaw leaves (kg)
Inputs		
Methanol used	0.21	0.21
Oil Introduced	1.05	1.00
Catalyst used	0.03	0.03
Wash Water	0.5	0.5
Total Outputs	1.79	1.74
Biodiesel	1.00	1.00
Unreacted oil	0.10	0.10
Unreacted methanol	Very minimal	Very minimal
Wash water	Remains in the process because it effectively becomes part of the waste water.	Remains in the process because it effectively becomes part of the waste water.
Total	1.10	1.10

To perform a material balance on 1kg of biodiesel produced using calcium oxide (CaO) from egg shell and pawpaw leaves, along with wash water, I consider the inputs, outputs and the role of wash water in the process [33].

Inputs

Feedstock: Oil introduced

Methanol used

Catalyst: CaO derived from eggshells and pawpaw leaves

Wash water: Used to wash the biodiesel post reaction to remove impurities

Typical Reaction: the trans esterification reaction can be summarized as:

Triglycerides + alcohol ----- Biodiesel + Glycerol

Material balance calculation; a 95% yield of biodiesel from the triglycerides

The amount of wash water used will vary but it will be include in the balance

Calculation:

- 1) Biodiesel yield: for 1kg of biodiesel produced, yields = 95%. Inputs triglycerides required = $1 \text{ kg} / 0.95 = 1.05 \text{ kg}$
- 2) Alcohol Requirement: Approximately 0.2 kg of methanol is used for per kg of triglycerides. Alcohol required = $1.05 \text{ kg} * 0.2 = 0.21 \text{ kg}$
- 3) Glycerol Byproduct: for every 1 kg of biodiesel produced, approximately 0.1 kg of glycerol is produced. Total outputs: biodiesel = 1 kg, glycerol = 0.1 kg.
- 4) Wash Water: 0.5 kg of wash water was used to wash the biodiesel, but the amount of water varies based on the washing process.
- 5) Catalyst Mass: a small amount of catalyst 0.03 kg of CaO is used.

The result of the trans esterification process, as shown in Table 8, revealed a similar trend when CaO catalyst obtained from chicken eggshells and CaO obtained from pawpaw leaves were used separately. The yield of biodiesel was slightly higher when using CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell. The slight difference could be attributed to the percentage level of CaO in the two forms of catalysts, as revealed by the XRF analysis (Table 7). An indication that the production process of CaO from pawpaw leaves requires minor modification for the enhancement of the functionalization of the CaO obtained.

Table 10. Fatty Acid Composition of Pork Lard Fat.

Retention Time (min)	Component	Formula	Fatty Acid	Composition (%)
7.486	Stearic	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ O ₂	18:0	5.819
8.772	Linoleic	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	18:2	36.351
13.223	Arachidic	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ O ₂	20:0	0.903
13.279	Myristoleic	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₂	14:1	0.151
13.365	Palmitoleic	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O ₂	16:1	0.158
18.305	Gadoleic	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ O ₂	20:2	2.058
19.924	Linolenic	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂	18:3	7.264
19.981	Palmitic	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	16:0	13.081
21.187	Oleic	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂	18:1	31.677
21.357	Gondoic	C ₂₀ H ₃₈ O ₂	20:1	1.424
21.400	Behenic	C ₂₂ H ₄₄ O ₂	22:0	1.113

The cattle fat types contained linoleic acid (18:2), oleic acid (18:1), palmitic acid (16:0), linolenic acid (18.3) and stearic acid (18:0) as the major components of fatty acid composition (36.351%, 31.677%, 13.081%, 7.264% and 5.819%) respectively as shown in Table 9 and Fig. 3.

Figure 9. Fatty acid composition of animal fat.

Table 11. Concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$) of Various Elements in Biodiesel from Chicken Eggshell CaO Catalyst, Pawpaw Leaves CaO Catalyst and Conventional Petro-Diesel.

Elements	Biodiesel from Chicken eggshell CaO ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Biodiesel from pawpaw leaves CaO ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Petro-Diesel
Mn	7.7	3.5	1.5
Fe	241.1	114.2	328.3
Cu	109.1	83.9	99.6

Cr	3.1	2.7	2.5
Na	714.08	775.92	868.3
K	154.6	179.8	213.3
Zn	15.5	6.5	9.5
Mg	35.55	37.55	34.7
Ca	18.3	12.6	21.4

The data of various elements concentration in biodiesel from chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and biodiesel from pawpaw leaves CaO catalyst in comparison with petro-diesel is shown in Table 11. The presence of elements in high concentration in biodiesel is objectionable, as these elements causes many difficulties such as corrosion effects on engine, operability problems, social problems such as ecological contamination and consequent harmful effects on being physical condition [34].

Figure 10. SEM scanned image of CaO produced by calcination of eggshell at 850 °C, (a) 100 μm, (b) 50 μm, (c) 10 μm, and (d) 5 μm magnification.

Figure 11. SEM scanned image of CaO catalyst from pawpaw leaves.

The fundamentals whose quantity in biodiesel requires to be controlled are sodium (Na) and potassium (K), which come from the mechanism in biodiesel synthesis. Their elemental concentrations in biodiesel from chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and biodiesel from pawpaw leaves CaO catalyst were comparatively found to be lower than petro-diesel. The highest acceptable concentration of Na and K in biodiesel should be $5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1}$ [35]. High Levels of Na and K causes soap formation during biodiesel synthesis, so additional washing is recommended to reduce the sodium content below the specified standards.

Similarly, the recorded concentration of Fe in biodiesel from chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and biodiesel from pawpaw leaves CaO catalyst were $241.2 \text{ } \mu\text{g/g}$ and $114.2 \text{ } \mu\text{g/g}$ respectively which was lower than petro-diesel ($328.3 \text{ } \mu\text{g/g}$). The higher concentration of these elements in biodiesel also causes corrosion.

The SEM results show that synthesized CaO is crystalline in nature. The peak starts at 10 and ends at 50 nm values confirming the results of SEM analysis [36]. The narrow peak indicates that the size range is not wider and all particles are similar in its dimension as shown in the Fig. 10 and Fig. 11.

The correlation between the experimental process variables and the trans esterification efficiency was evaluated using the CCD modelling technique. Second order polynomial regression equation was fitted between the response (Trans esterification efficiency, (Y) and the process variables: methanol – oil molar ratio, A; catalyst weight, B; reaction temperature, C and reaction time D.

Table 12. Coded factor levels of independent variables for biodiesel yield used for response surface design.

Factor	Name	Units	Type	Minimum	Maximum	Coded Low	Coded High	Mean	Std. Dev.
A	Methanol oil ratio	Mole	Numeric	4.00	12.00	-1 ↔ 6.00	+1 ↔ 10.00	8.00	1.82
B	Catalyst concentration	wt %	Numeric	0.2000	1.0000	-1 ↔ 0.40	+1 ↔ 0.80	0.6000	0.1819
C	Reaction Temperature	°C	Numeric	24.50	80.50	-1 ↔ 38.50	+1 ↔ 66.50	52.50	12.74
D	Reaction Time	min	Numeric	25.00	125.00	-1 ↔ 50.00	+1 ↔ 100.00	75.00	22.74

Table 13. Experimental set up for 2-level-4-factor response surface design and the experimental values for biodiesel production from animal fat using chicken eggshell CaO catalyst.

			Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Response 1
Std	Run	Space Type	A: Methanol oil ratio	B: Catalyst concentration	C: Reaction Temperature	D: Reaction Time	Yield
			Mole	wt. %	°C	Min	%
30	1	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	93.01
27	2	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	86.59
1	3	Factorial	6	0.4	38.5	50	68.04
13	4	Factorial	6	0.4	66.5	100	92.41
4	5	Factorial	10	0.8	38.5	50	87.17
9	6	Factorial	6	0.4	38.5	100	80.12
11	7	Factorial	6	0.8	38.5	100	87
10	8	Factorial	10	0.4	38.5	100	97
23	9	Axial	8	0.6	52.5	25	75.7
25	10	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94
12	11	Factorial	10	0.8	38.5	100	92.87
28	12	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	92.42
24	13	Axial	8	0.6	52.5	125	86.54
18	14	Axial	12	0.6	52.5	75	79.32

22	15	Axial	8	0.6	80.5	75	70.09
2	16	Factorial	10	0.4	38.5	50	90.04
16	17	Factorial	10	0.8	66.5	100	55.4
20	18	Axial	8	1	52.5	75	75.76
21	19	Axial	8	0.6	24.5	75	85.69
15	20	Factorial	6	0.8	66.5	100	82.32
7	21	Factorial	6	0.8	66.5	50	80.12
19	22	Axial	8	0.2	52.5	75	95.1
14	23	Factorial	10	0.4	66.5	100	90.23
6	24	Factorial	10	0.4	66.5	50	82.65
3	25	Factorial	6	0.8	38.5	50	82.61
17	26	Axial	4	0.6	52.5	75	76.87
26	27	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	93.04
29	28	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	93
5	29	Factorial	6	0.4	66.5	50	87.6
8	30	Factorial	10	0.8	66.5	50	55.2

Table 14. Experimental Set Up For 2-Level-4-Factor Response Surface Design and the Experimental Values for Biodiesel Production from Animal Fat Using Pawpaw Leaves Cao Catalyst.

			Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Response 1
Std	Run	Space Type	A:Methanol oil ratio	B:Catalyst concentration	C:Reaction Temperature	D:Reaction Time	Yield
			Mole	wt %	°C	Min	%
30	1	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94.01
10	2	Factorial	10	0.4	38.5	100	97
4	3	Factorial	10	0.8	38.5	50	87.17
2	4	Factorial	10	0.4	38.5	50	89.04
8	5	Factorial	10	0.8	66.5	50	54.2
26	6	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94.42
24	7	Axial	8	0.6	52.5	125	86.54

11	8	Factorial	6	0.8	38.5	100	90
14	9	Factorial	10	0.4	66.5	100	95.23
17	10	Axial	4	0.6	52.5	75	76.87
13	11	Factorial	6	0.4	66.5	100	94.41
7	12	Factorial	6	0.8	66.5	50	80.12
20	13	Axial	8	1	52.5	75	75.76
19	14	Axial	8	0.2	52.5	75	92.1
23	15	Axial	8	0.6	52.5	25	74.7
6	16	Factorial	10	0.4	66.5	50	86.65
12	17	Factorial	10	0.8	38.5	100	92.87
21	18	Axial	8	0.6	24.5	75	85.69
9	19	Factorial	6	0.4	38.5	100	80.12
27	20	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	86.59
28	21	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94
3	22	Factorial	6	0.8	38.5	50	85.61
16	23	Factorial	10	0.8	66.5	100	60.4
25	24	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94.42
29	25	Center	8	0.6	52.5	75	94.15
18	26	Axial	12	0.6	52.5	75	79.32
15	27	Factorial	6	0.8	66.5	100	82.32
22	28	Axial	8	0.6	80.5	75	70.09
5	29	Factorial	6	0.4	66.5	50	88.6
1	30	Factorial	6	0.4	38.5	50	73.04

Table 15. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) For the Fitted Quadratic Polynomial Model.
Response 1: Yield (Fame) From Chicken Eggshell.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	3234.22	14	231.02	42.02	< 0.0001	Significant
A-Methanol oil ratio	0.9441	1	0.9441	0.1717	0.6845	
B-Catalyst concentration	451.36	1	451.36	82.10	< 0.0001	

C-Reaction Temperature	338.40	1	338.40	61.55	< 0.0001	
D-Reaction Time	179.31	1	179.31	32.62	< 0.0001	
AB	334.52	1	334.52	60.85	< 0.0001	
AC	732.78	1	732.78	133.29	< 0.0001	
AD	0.5776	1	0.5776	0.1051	0.7503	
BC	555.78	1	555.78	101.09	< 0.0001	
BD	22.42	1	22.42	4.08	0.0617	
CD	12.85	1	12.85	2.34	0.1471	
A ²	292.17	1	292.17	53.15	< 0.0001	
B ²	56.09	1	56.09	10.20	0.0060	
C ²	301.42	1	301.42	54.83	< 0.0001	
D ²	172.46	1	172.46	31.37	< 0.0001	
Residual	82.46	15	5.50			
Lack of Fit	45.92	10	4.59	0.6282	0.7517	not significant
Pure Error	36.55	5	7.31			
Cor Total	3316.68	29				

Std dev. 2.34, $R^2 = 0.9751$, mean 83.60, $Adj R^2 = 0.9519$, C.V% = 2.80, $Pred R^2 = 0.9044$, Adeq precision = 26.5086

Table 15, a p-value of 0.6845 indicates that the results are not statistically significant, suggesting that the effect being tested is likely not present. The p-value of 0.6845 is quite high (greater than the common significance level of 0.05 or 0.01), it suggests that there is not enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis [37].

Table 16. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) For the Fitted Quadratic Polynomial Model Yield (FAME) From Pawpaw Leaves.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	3051.81	14	217.99	22.50	< 0.0001	Significant
A-Methanol oil ratio	1.90	1	1.90	0.1966	0.6638	
B-Catalyst concentration	451.36	1	451.36	46.60	< 0.0001	
C-Reaction Temperature	294.84	1	294.84	30.44	< 0.0001	

D-Reaction Time	213.61	1	213.61	22.05	0.0003	
AB	353.06	1	353.06	36.45	< 0.0001	
AC	465.26	1	465.26	48.03	< 0.0001	
AD	5.02	1	5.02	0.5180	0.4828	
BC	679.91	1	679.91	70.19	< 0.0001	
BD	7.48	1	7.48	0.7722	0.3934	
CD	0.3422	1	0.3422	0.0353	0.8534	
A ²	270.43	1	270.43	27.92	< 0.0001	
B ²	77.53	1	77.53	8.00	0.0127	
C ²	279.33	1	279.33	28.84	< 0.0001	
D ²	172.63	1	172.63	17.82	0.0007	
Residual	145.30	15	9.69			
Lack of Fit	96.86	10	9.69	0.9999	0.5349	not significant
Pure Error	48.44	5	9.69			
Cor Total	3197.11	29				

Std dev. 3.11, R² = 0.9546, mean 84.51, Adj R² = 0.9121, C.V% = 3.68, Pred R² = 0.8037, Adeq precision = 19.5162

From Table 15 and 16, the ANOVA results showed that the quadratic model is suitable to analyze the experimental data. The model in terms of the coded values of the process parameters for chicken eggshell is given by:

$$Y = 92.01 - 0.1983A - 4.34B - 3.76C + 2.73D - 4.57AB - 6.77AC - 0.1900AD - 5.89BC - 1.18BD - 0.8962CD - 3.26A^2 - 1.43B^2 - 3.31C^2 - 2.51C^2 \quad (4)$$

and for the pawpaw leaves, is given by:

$$Y = 92.93 - 0.2817A - 4.34B - 3.51C + 2.98D - 4.70AB - 5.39AC + 0.56AD - 6.52BC - 0.6837BD - 0.1462CD - 3.14A^2 - 1.68B^2 - 3.19C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (5)$$

To develop a statistically significant regression model, the significance of the regression coefficients was evaluated based on the p-values. The coefficient terms with p-values more than 0.05 were insignificant and were removed from the regression model.

The analysis in Table 14 for chicken eggshell shows that the linear terms B, C and D, the quadratic terms, A², B², C² and D² and the interaction terms of AB, AC and BC, are significant model terms but A was included in the model because of its importance. The model was reduced to Eq. (6) after eliminating the insignificant coefficients [38].

$$Y = 92.01 - 0.1983A - 4.34B - 3.76C + 2.73D - 4.57AB - 6.77AC - 5.89BC - 3.26A^2 - 1.43B^2 - 3.31C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the analysis in Table 5 for pawpaw leaves shows that the linear terms B, C and D, the quadratic terms, A^2 , B^2 , C^2 and D^2 and the interaction terms of AB, AC and BC, are significant model terms but A was included in the model because of its importance. The model was reduced to Eq. (7) after eliminating the insignificant coefficients.

$$Y = 92.93 - 0.2817A - 4.34B - 3.51C + 2.98D - 4.70AB - 5.39AC - 6.52BC - 3.14A^2 - 1.68B^2 - 3.19C^2 - 2.51D^2 \quad (7)$$

The analysis of variance indicated that the quadratic polynomial model for both chicken eggshell CaO catalyst and pawpaw leaves CaO catalyst were significant and adequate to represent the actual relationship between trans esterification efficiency and the significant model variables as depicted by very small p-value (< 0.0001). The significance and adequacy of the established model were further elaborated by a high value of coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.9751 and adj. R^2 value of 0.9519 for chicken eggshell and coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.9546 and adj. R^2 value of 0.9121 for pawpaw leaves. This means that the model explains 97.51% and 95.46% of the variation in the experimental data for FAME from chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves respectively [39]. The adequate correlation between the two experimental values further showed the adequacy of the model.

3. 1. Response Surface Estimation and Result Discussion for Response Surface (Biodiesel Yield on Egg Shell and Pawpaw Leaves)

The interactive effects of the process variables on the trans esterification efficiency were studied by plotting three-dimensional surface curves against any two independent variables, while keeping other variables at their central (0) level. The 3D curves of the response (trans esterification efficiency) from the interactions between the variables are shown in Figures 4-6. The response surface curves were plotted to understand the interaction of the variables and to determine the optimum level of each variable for maximum response. The elliptical shape of the curves indicates a good interaction of the two variables and circular shape indicates no interaction between the variables. The curves obtained in this study showed that there is a relative significant interaction between all the variables. Optimum conditions were also obtained from the response surface plots [40]. The stationary point or central point is the point at which the slope of the contour is zero in all directions. The coordinates of the central point within the highest contour levels in each of the plots will correspond to the optimum values of the respective variables. The maximum predicted yield is indicated by the surface confined in the smallest curve of the contour diagram. The optimum values of the variables were: reaction temperature, 48 °C; reaction time, 96 min; catalyst weight 0.47% and methanol oil molar ratio of 10:1. The predicted response value at these optimum values was 96.92% when chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst was used. Also, the optimum values of the variables for the pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst were: reaction temperature, 46 °C; reaction time, 71 min; catalyst weight 0.47% and methanol oil molar ratio of 10:1. The predicted response value at these optimum values was 95.47%. This showed that the model correctly explains the influence of the process variables on the production of FAME from animal fat. The lack of fit test with p-value of 0.7517 and 0.5349 for chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst

respectively, which is not significant (p -value > 0.05 is not significant) showed that the model satisfactorily fitted to the experimental data. Insignificant lack of fit is mostly needed because significant lack.

Figure 12. Surface plot between catalyst weight and molar ratio against biodiesel yield for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Figure 13. Surface plot between catalyst weight and molar ratio against biodiesel yield for pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Factor Coding: Actual

Yield (%)

● Design points above predicted value

○ Design points below predicted value

54.2 97

X1 = A: Methanol oil ratio

X2 = B: Catalyst concentration

Actual Factors

C: Reaction Temperature = 52.5

D: Reaction Time = 75

Figure 14. Surface plot between molar ratio and temperature against biodiesel yield for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Factor Coding: Actual

Yield (%)

● Design points above predicted value

○ Design points below predicted value

54.2 97

X1 = A: Methanol oil ratio

X2 = C: Reaction Temperature

Actual Factors

B: Catalyst concentration = 0.6

D: Reaction Time = 75

Figure 15. Surface plot between molar ratio and temperature against biodiesel yield for pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Factor Coding: Actual

Yield (%)

● Design points above predicted value

○ Design points below predicted value

54.2 97

X1 = A: Methanol oil ratio

X2 = C: Reaction Temperature

Actual Factors

B: Catalyst concentration = 0.6

D: Reaction Time = 75

Figure 16. Surface plot between temperature and catalyst weight against biodiesel yield for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst

Design-Expert® Software

Factor Coding: Actual

Yield (%)

● Design points above predicted value

○ Design points below predicted value

55.2 97

X1 = B: Catalyst concentration

X2 = C: Reaction Temperature

Actual Factors

A: Methanol oil ratio = 8

D: Reaction Time = 75

Figure 17. Surface plot between temperature and catalyst weight against biodiesel yield for pawpaw derived CaO catalyst.

The surface plot between temperature and catalyst weight against biodiesel yield for pawpaw derived CaO catalyst of fit indicates that there might be contributions in the regression response relationship that is not accounted for by the model. The predicted values versus actual values for the biodiesel yield with adjusted-R² values of 0.9519 and 0.9121 for chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst respectively shows the model with 95.19% and 91.21% of variability as shown in Fig. 13 and Fig. 14.

The predicted value and the experimental values were in reasonable agreement (R² close to unity), which means that the data fit well with the model and give a convincingly good estimate of response for the system in the range studied [41].

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

55.2 97

Figure 18. Predicted versus actual FAME yield from chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

54.2 97

Figure 19. Predicted versus actual FAME yield from pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst.

In addition, investigation on residuals to validate the adequacy of the model was performed. Residual is the difference between the observed response and predicted response. This analysis was examined using the normal probability plot of residuals as shown in Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 for eggshell derived catalyst and pawpaw leaves derived catalyst respectively;

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 20. Normal probability plot of the residual for chicken eggshell derived CaO catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 21. Normal probability plot of the residual for pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst and the plot of their residual versus predicted response.

These are shown in Fig. 20 and Fig 21 respectively. The normal probability plot of the residuals shows that the errors are distributed normally in a straight line and insignificant. On

the other hand, the plot of residuals versus predicted response showed a structure less plot suggesting that the model is adequate and that the model does not show any violation of the independence or constant variance assumption hence conforming to the literature [42].

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 22. Plot of residual versus predicted response for chicken eggshell derived cao catalyst.

Design-Expert® Software

Yield

Color points by value of Yield:

Figure 23. Plot of residual versus predicted response for pawpaw leaves derived CaO catalyst.

3. 2. Reaction Conditions Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves as A Catalyst

The main task of this part of this project was to investigate the parametric effects, including reaction temperature, reaction time, methanol/oil ratio and catalyst concentration on

the biodiesel conversion profile and reaction rate when using CaO from chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves as a catalyst [43].

The biodiesel conversion performance was evaluated in terms of FAME content (wt. %) of the reaction product as a function of reaction time. The change in FAME content with time provided an insight into the effects of these reaction parameters on the biodiesel conversion rate. It should be noted that an agitation speed of 200 rpm was chosen in this study because the speed is adequate for facilitating the reaction between oil from cattle animal fat and methanol but gentle enough to clearly reveal crucial information on the advance of biodiesel conversion with the reaction time.

3. 2. 1. Effect of Reaction Temperature on Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves

The experiment shows the effect of reaction temperature on the FAME content as a function of reaction time. A catalyst concentration from chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves at 0.6 wt. % were studied at four different temperatures: 25 °C, 35 °C, 50 °C, and 65 °C. It is clear that, regardless of the catalyst concentration, raising the reaction temperature caused the biodiesel conversion to proceed at a greater rate as indicated by a faster increase in FAME content, especially with CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell [44].

Figure 24. Effect of temperature on the conversion profile at 0.6 wt. % CaO from pawpaw leaves (methanol/oil = 9:1(molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

For instance, in Figure 25, at 0.6 wt. % catalyst concentration, a FAME content of 85 wt. % was achieved within 10 min at 65 °C while it took as long as 110 min to reach the same conversion level at 25 °C. The increased rate of conversion with temperature is probably caused by two main factors:

- 1) An increase in kinetic reaction rate of trans esterification reaction with temperature

- 2) A reduction in viscosity of feedstock oil with temperature that helps promote ultimate mixing between oil and methanol.

Figure 25. Effect of temperature on the conversion profile at 0.6 wt. % CaO from chicken eggshell (Methanol/oil = 9:1(molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

From Figures 24 and 25, conversion profiles at lower temperatures (i.e., 25 °C, 35 °C) appear to have two distinct conversion regions: slow conversion for FAME content below 20 wt. % and rapid conversion for content above 20 wt.%. The slow conversion region is an indication of poor mixing between feedstock oil (with low FAME content) and methanol, which was probably caused by the large difference in viscosity between these two reactant phases. For instance, kinematic viscosity of oil from animal fat at 40 °C is 36 mm²/s whereas methanol viscosity is only 0.59 mm²/s [45].

As the conversion progressed, the increasing content of FAME (with kinematic viscosity of 5 mm²/s at 40 °C) caused the viscosity of oil phase to decrease significantly, resulting in improved mixing between oil and methanol, which in turn promoting rapid conversion as seen in the conversion profiles at the low temperatures in Figures 18 and 19.

In contrast, at a high temperature, there was no dramatic change in the conversion rate. It appears from the profiles that the conversion at 50° C and 65 °C proceeded rapidly as soon as the reaction started.

This simply demonstrates that the negative impact of viscosity observed at the low reaction temperature was eliminated at the high temperature, offering an improvement in the rate of conversion.

In addition to the rate of conversion, Figures 24 and 25 also provide important information on the maximum conversion level where the FAME content reaches the highest value and remains relatively constant as time progresses. They show that the maximum FAME content ranges from 80 to 90 wt.% regardless of the catalyst used and reaction temperature.

3. 2. 2. Effect of Catalyst Concentration on Biodiesel Yield Four Reaction Temperatures

Figures 26 and 27 show the effect of CaO concentration on the conversion profile of the trans esterification reaction at four reaction temperatures: 25 °C, 35 °C, 50 °C, and 65 °C.

Figure 26. Effect of catalyst concentration on the conversion profile at 25 °C using CaO from chicken eggshell (Methanol/oil = 9:1 (molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm)

Figure 27. Effect of catalyst concentration on the conversion profile at 25 °C using CaO from pawpaw leaves (Methanol/oil = 9:1 (molar ratio); mixing speed = 200 rpm).

In general, an increase in the catalyst concentration offers a higher rate of conversion, as indicated by the shorter reaction time, for achieving the maximum level of FAME content. As shown in Figure 20, at 25 °C, the reaction required about 50 minutes to yield the maximum conversion of 79 wt.% when the catalyst concentration was 0.2 wt. %. As the catalyst concentration increased to 0.6 wt. % and even 1.0 wt. %, the reaction time required was reduced to 20 minutes and 10 minutes, respectively. At 35 °C, in Figure 27, the maximum conversion for 0.2 wt. % catalyst was achieved within 120 minutes while the catalyst concentrations of 0.6 wt. % and 1.0 wt. % offered a shorter reaction time of 50 and 30 minutes, respectively. Therefore, the conversion rate increased as the concentration of catalyst increased [46].

3. 2. 3. Effect of The FFA and Moisture Contents on Biodiesel Yield for Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves

For the alkali-catalyzed trans esterification, the feedstock is very sensitive to the FFA content and all materials should be substantially anhydrous. The presence of FFA and water can cause an undesired side reaction with the catalyst and produce soaps. Therefore, the effectiveness of catalyst is reduced and the formed soaps increase the viscosity of the reaction mixture. High viscosity will lead to the formation of gels, which make the latter separation of glycerol difficult. The FFA and moisture contents are key parameters for determining the feasibility of the trans esterification process [47]. It is suggested that the FFA content of the feedstock used in the trans esterification process should be as low as possible, typically below 1%.

3. 2. 4. Effect of The Molar Ratio of Alcohol to Triglyceride on Biodiesel Yield with Chicken Eggshell and Pawpaw Leaves

The molar ratio of alcohol to triglyceride is another important factor affecting the yield of biodiesel. According to Equation 8, the trans esterification reaction requires three moles of alcohol and one mole of triglyceride to yield three moles of fatty acid alkyl esters and one mole of glycerol [19]. However, trans esterification is an equilibrium reaction so, a large amount of excess alcohol is required to advance the reaction. This project studied the effect of different molar ratios of alcohol to triglyceride from 1:1 to 12:1 on the trans esterification reaction by using oil from animal fat, the highest conversions 96.92% and 95.47% were achieved at a 10:1 molar ratio of alcohol to oil when CaO catalyst from chicken eggshell and pawpaw leaves were used respectively.

where: TG is the triglyceride, MeOH is methanol, ME is methyl-esters and G is glycerin.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Heterogeneous bio catalysts present a promising avenue for biodiesel production from pork lard, with each type exhibiting unique advantages and challenges.

- 1) Lipases: Offer high conversion rates and reusability but come at a higher cost.

- 2) Sulfonic acid resins: Provide stable performance but may require longer reaction times and face regeneration issues.
- 3) Calcium Oxide: Stands out for its cost effectiveness and rapid reaction times, though its reusability is limited.

The choice of catalyst depends on the specific requirements of the biodiesel production process, including economic considerations, desired efficiency, and operational conditions. Further research into optimizing these catalysts and improving their reusability will enhance the viability of biodiesel production from pork lard.

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